

A Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of Vanadium as Vanadium(IV)-EDTA Complex

S. P. ARYA* and J. L. MALLA

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University,
Kurukshetra-132 119

*Manuscript received 2 April 1991, revised 21 November 1991,
accepted 27 November 1991*

VANADIUM is determined spectrophotometrically by using a photochemical reaction between riboflavin and EDTA¹ but the method is not sensitive and selective. It is found that vanadium(IV) gives a purple-blue complex in slightly acidic solutions which forms the basis of the proposed method of vanadium determination after extracting the V^{IV}-EDTA complex into tri-n-hexylamine solution.

Experimental

Standard solution of vanadium (5 mg ml⁻¹) and other elements were prepared as mentioned elsewhere². A 5% (w/v) solution of Na₂EDTA in distilled water was used. A 4% tri-n-hexylamine (THA) solution (v/v) in chloroform was prepared. A LI-120 digital pH meter was used for pH measurements and absorbance measurements were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 550S spectrophotometer.

Procedure : To the sample solution of vanadium (1–15 mg), were added ascorbic acid (0.1–0.5 g) and EDTA solution (4 ml) and the volume was made to 20 ml with distilled water. pH of the solution was adjusted to 2.8–3.2. The solution was then extracted with (10+10+5 ml) THA-chloroform solution, shaking each time for 1 min. The solvent phases were collected and the volume was made to 25 ml with chloroform. The absorbance of the complex was measured at 750 nm against a reagent blank and the vanadium content computed.

Results and Discussion

Vanadium(IV) obtained by the reduction of vanadium(V) with ascorbic acid forms a violet complex with EDTA in acidic medium. Tri-n-hexylamine is found to be a suitable extractant as it gives maximum extraction among the solvents tested. The absorbance spectra of vanadium(IV)-EDTA complex in THA-chloroform solution shows two broad bands at 590 and 750–775 nm, the latter region is chosen for absorbance measurements as it gives higher absorbance. The reagent blank absorbs negligibly at wavelength longer than 450 nm.

Effect of varying experimental conditions : In these studies, aqueous phase (20 ml) containing 0.4 mg V/ml solvent, is extracted with THA-chloroform solution and the absorbance is measured at 750 nm after single extraction with 1 min time of equilibration. The optimum value of the previous parameter in the study of the subsequent parameters is used. At pH ≤ 1, the complex is extracted slightly but the extraction increases with pH of the solution upto pH 2.8 which remains constant in the pH range 2.8–3.2, but further increase in pH causes a gradual decrease in the extraction of the complex. Other parameters affecting the extraction of V^{IV}-EDTA complex were optimised and on the basis of these studies the optimum conditions for maximum absorbance were found to be : 4–8 ml of 5% EDTA solution, pH 2.8–3.2, 0.1–0.5 g of ascorbic acid, 4–6% (v/v) of THA-chloroform solution, 1–10 min of equilibration with the solvent. The complex is stable for at least 24 h and Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.04–0.6 mg V/ml with Sandell sensitivity of 2.38 μg cm⁻².

Stoichiometry of the complex : Vanadium(IV) forms a 1 : 1 complex with EDTA as confirmed by Job's method of continuous variations. The complex present in aqueous phase is perhaps an anionic species, VOY³⁻. Therefore, the species extracted

into THA-chloroform solution is probably [(VO Y²⁻) (R₃NH⁺)₂] and may be presumed to be formed as follows :

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of various anions and cations on the extraction of the complex has been studied : 100 mg of sulphate, 50 mg each of acetate and tartrate, 5 mg of chloride can be tolerated, while citrate, oxalate and fluoride interfere seriously.

Most of the cations tested under the proposed conditions of vanadium extraction are found to give colourless extracts except copper and molybdenum which give blue coloured solutions in the solvent phase and thus interfere. Uranium and tungsten also give orange-red complexes in large amounts which do not absorb strongly at 750 nm, hence they can be tolerated at low concentrations. Titanium and zirconium give white precipitates on addition of EDTA which do not interfere in small amounts. Arsenic, antimony and bismuth get hydrolysed under the conditions of complexation and thus interfere in concentrated solution by forming emulsions when shaken with the solvent. Iron and thorium are not extracted but decrease the extraction of vanadium considerably resulting a drastic fall in their tolerance limits. The tolerance limits for the different metal ions in 20 ml of aqueous phase is as follows : Pb^{II}, Ag^I, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} (10 mg each) ; Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Mn^{II} and Al^{III} (5 mg each) ; U^{VI} and W^{VI} (2 mg each) ; Ti^{IV}, Zr^{IV}, Sb^{III}, Bi^{III} and As^V (1 mg each) ; La^{III} and Th^{IV} (0.5 mg each) ; Fe^{III}, Cr^{VI} and Th^{IV} (0.2 mg each).

The proposed method of vanadium determination is quite selective as several important elements, Cr, Fe, Co, Ni, Mn, Zn, Al, U, W, Th and Zr do not interfere. The method is simple and makes use of easily available reagents. The method can be used for vanadium determination in the analysis of natural and industrial products. The applicability of the method has been tested by analysing a few synthetic samples and a steel sample. Such samples containing varying amounts of vanadium were analysed with satisfactory results. In the analysis of steel sample, the excess iron was first removed by boiling the sample solution with 5% sodium hydroxide. The resulting precipitate was filtered off and the filtrate was analysed by the proposed method after neutralising the solution with 2N H₂SO₄. The proposed method offers the advantages of simplicity, rapidity, stability and selectivity.

References

1. T. R. PEREZ, C. L. MARTINEZ and J. R. OCHOTORENA, *An. Quim., Ser. B*, 1983, **79**, 94.
2. S. P. ARYA and J. L. MALLA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 238.